

Space Time Slices in Quantum and Classical Mechanics Part II

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In part I of this note, we argued that in quantum bound states one has a notion of dx and dt associated with p and E i.e. $dx \rightarrow 1/p$ and $dt \rightarrow 1/E$, but not of continuous time associated with particle motion. $\exp(-iEt)$ contains time t , but this refers to a cycling time associated with various $\exp(ipx)$ free particle probabilities combining with $\exp(ikx)$ to form $\exp(ipx)$. In other words there is a certain time resolution as well as a space resolution (wavelength) for the single particle and time t refers to the entire quantum resonance. In a bound system, there is also a $v_{rms}(x)$ which holds for every quantum energy state E_n and this is linked to a continuous space time picture i.e. $x(t)$. It is this $x(t)$ which gives a sense of past, present and future. A quantum system, however, is a statistical system much like $V(x)$ a potential. It does not follow a particle from one x to another in space because the potential renders stochastic hits. It is only interested in the overall resonance which forms. "t" in $\exp(-iEt)$ is associated with this resonance and not with single particle motion. Thus there is no classical sense of past, present or future in the quantum bound state at least with respect to the single particle. An entire quantum system may, however, evolve, but a bound system simply cycles through time. The single particle has no time attributes except dt associated with $1/E$ where $E = p^2/2m$.

In part 1 we argued that p may be thought of in terms of impulse (hits). In such a case it is not directly linked to space and time. We also argued that $p = m_0 v$ even in the quantum case so dx and dt must be present indirectly. In this note we revisit these ideas by following (1) and deriving quantum mechanical behaviour for a free particle from the classical Lagrangian equations $dL/dx (\text{partial}) = p$ and $H = pv - L$. This directly shows that a quantum picture deals with dx and dt for a single free particle and so the idea of $x(t)$ only holds in an rms sense. For a single free particle, matters differ from the bound case because $p = m_0 v_{rms}$ (free particle). Thus we argue that $\exp(ipx)$ must be viewed in terms of probability and is only manifest if an interaction occurs. Such interactions, however, may be continuously occurring as in the case of the Bohm Aharonov effect in which there is a magnetic vector potential existing in a large region of space.

Quantum Free Particle From Classical Lagrangian

In classical physics, motion is obtained from Lagrange equations (which reproduce Newton's laws). Two relationships associated with this formalism are:

$$dL/dx (\text{partial}) = p (\text{momentum}) \quad \text{and} \quad H = px - L \quad \text{where } H \text{ the Hamiltonian is often energy ((1))}$$

For a free particle, one may consider the classical action = $\int dt L = T - L$. Then:

$$dAction/dx (\text{partial}) = T \quad dAction/dT (\text{partial}) = p \quad \text{or} \quad dAction/dx (\text{partial}) = dAction/dv \quad dv/dx (\text{partial})$$

where $dv/dx (\text{partial}) = 1/T$. Furthermore $dAction/dt (\text{partial}) = -E$ or

$$d\text{Action}/dt \text{ partial} = L + T \quad dL/dt \text{ partial} = L + T \quad dL/dv \quad dv/dt \text{ partial} = L + T(-1/TT) \quad p = -px + L$$

These relationships have been shown in (1). Thus classical Lagrangian formalism contains for a free particle:

$$d\text{Action}/dt \text{ partial} = -E \quad \text{and} \quad d\text{Action}/dx = p \quad ((2))$$

This is an unusual approach, however, because one takes d/dt and d/dx without any link between x and t i.e. ignoring $x(t)$ or $v = \text{constant} = X/T$. No Lagrange multiplier is introduced. This suggests dx and dt values associated with E and p , yet for a constant velocity one has the continuous expression $v = x/t$.

One may make the idea of dx and dt associated with E and p explicit from ((2)) (which is still a classical equation) in the following way. Create the function $\exp(i \text{Action})$ and use it in a classical expression linking energy and momentum i.e. $E = pp/2m$ (free particle) or $EE = pp + \text{momo}$ relativistically. For the nonrelativistic case:

$$i \, d/dt \exp(i \text{Action}) = 1/2m \, d/dx \, d/dx \exp(i \text{Action}) \quad ((3)) \quad \text{free particle}$$

One has taken a classical equation and created a quantum one i.e. the Schrodinger equation ((3)). $\exp(i \text{Action})$ is equivalent to $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ so one immediately has periodicity in space and time i.e. space and time resolution proportional to $1/p$ and $1/E$. In other words there is spatial and time resolution not exact time and space points as in classical physics. Dx divided by dt , however, should still yield v . In other words v is a kind of averaged quantity in space which does not reflect the granularity of dx and dt which are directly tied to p and E . Equation ((3)) is a probabilistic one in the sense that there are dx and dt intervals rather than continuous points. The idea of past, present and future seems to break down within these regions.

It is interesting to note that for an electron which is a quantum object, classical notions may still hold. For example an electron source may exist at a point x_1 and produce an electron at t_1 . This electron will have a constant velocity and will move seemingly like a classical particle passing x_2 at t_2 etc. One may then ask: What is the relevance of dx and dt ? Dx and dt , however, are fully relevant if the quantum free particle interacts. For example, in the Bohm Aharonov experiment where there is a magnetic vector potential A , but no magnetic field in a region of space, interactions with a free particle occur even though there is no acceleration. Thus for a quantum free particle there is a classical v_{rms} which is equal to p/m and is defined continuously at each x and t i.e. $v = x/t$. There, however, is also a probabilistic scenario associated with dx and dt regions in which one does not have continuous x and t , but rather probability. Thus there is no well defined past, present and future in this region. Matters become more complicated in the bound state case.

Quantum Bound State

The quantum bound state is treated as a distribution of conditional probability terms $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. $W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \, a(p) \exp(ipx)$. One may note that there is no time in this expression because one does not follow a particle in time. The wavefunction $W(x)$ has an

overall $\exp(-iEt)$ factor which describes the evolution of the resonance. The resonance, however, is between the particle and a potential $V(x)$ and is not associated with continuous motion $x(t)$ of the particle. The potential $V(x)$ which appears to be completely classical is really stochastic $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ and may deliver impulse hits to the right and left ($k, -k$) even though overall the average force is in one direction. Thus various stochastic hits occur and one cannot trace the particle in time because these are probabilistic in addition to the dx and dt probabilistic regions.

It may be noted that a quantum bound particle has a $v_{rms}(x)$ which is the classical $v(x)$ i.e.

$$KE_{classical}(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad (4) \quad \text{where } KE_{classical}(x) = [-1/2m d/dx dW/dx]/W$$

$v_{rms}(x)$ is associated with continuous time and space i.e. $x(t)$ and one does not need to consider dx and dt linked to $1/p$ and $1/E$. $v_{rms}(x)$, however, is a kind of average and so does not correspond to any actual physical motion of the particle.

Behaviour of $V_{rms}(t)$

Classical physics (e.g. the Lagrangian formalism-Newton's laws) yields equations for $v_{rms}(t)$ i.e. $x(t)$. In such a case, one knows about the past, present and future. For example, for an oscillator everything is predictable, but there are still two possible solutions. For example, at $t=0$ the oscillator particle may have been at either A or $-A$ where A is the amplitude. There are thus two solutions at each x , one moving to the right and one to the left (for a horizontal oscillator). Both of these satisfy the same conservation of energy equation. The two solutions are associated with present/past and future. For example, if at $t=0$ at $x=A$ then one solution at x at t describes the current motion and its past, but the other describes future motion at the same x . The second solution contains the same t , but it is equivalent to the first solution with $t+\text{phase}$ such that the phase yields a negative velocity at x .

In quantum mechanics, one has $v_{rms}(x)$ and so two solutions exist, but only for this average quantity. One does not have two solutions for the wavefunction which contains both $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. There is no ordered motion in terms of $x(t)$ for the quantum single particle. Rather there is ordered motion for the entire system i.e. the resonance. At best the quantum particle has a dt and dx intervals proportional to $1/p$ and $1/E$ where $E=pp/2m$. The entire resonance has a time resolution proportional to $1/E_n$. Thus in a probabilistic system the notion of past, present and future for a single particle may not make sense.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the idea of past, present and future for a particle are associated with defined motion i.e. $x(t)$ which is the ordered motion of classical mechanics. If one considers a conservation of energy equation, there are two solutions for $v(t)$ depending on initial conditions. In other words, one solution is like the present/past and the other like the future e.g. oscillator which starts at A versus $-A$ where A is the amplitude.

We note that classical Lagrangian expressions use d/dx and d/dt , but these imply independent changes of x and t for a free particle. If that is the case, there seems to be a

resolution dx and dt which may not be associated with a continuous x - t space. In particular we show that classical Lagrangian solutions may yield a math solution $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ where $E = p^2/2m$ for a conservation of energy equation. In such a case there are specific x and t resolutions of $1/p$ and $1/E$ which are not linked to continuous x - t space. Within these regions, one has probability not deterministic motion so there is no past, present and future. One may note that p and $-p$ may be used to create two solutions like the two vrms solutions of a classical system. If one creates a bound system, however, $\exp(-ipx)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ are both used in $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and so one has both forward and backwards motion. For every energy level E_n , the time-independent Schrodinger equation contains a vrms(x) = $[-1/2m \text{ } d/dx \text{ } dW/dx]/W$, but this is an average and does not describe actual particle motion. vrms(x) is associated with two solutions, but $W(x)$ is not at least in terms of forward or backwards motion. $W(x)$ contains both $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. There is thus no ordered back-forth motion in a bound state that one finds associated with $x(t)$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Differing Interpretations of the Lagrangian in Classical and Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2021)